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DEVELOPMENT & VALIDATION OF STABILITY INDICATING HPTLC METHOD FOR RILPIVIRINE & DOLUTEGRAVIR SODIUM IN COMBINATION

Mrinalini C. Damle^{*}, Amita N. Pardeshi

All India Shri Shivaji Memorial Society's College of Pharmacy, Kennedy Road, Near RTO, Pune-411001.

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To develop and validate stability indicating HPTLC method for determination of Rilpivirine and Dolutegravir Sodium Methods: The chromatographic development was carried out on aluminum plates pre-coated with silica gel 60 F254 as stationary phase using Toluene: Methanol: Ethyl acetate: Tri Ethyl Amine (5.5:1:1.5:0.1 v/v/v/v) as mobile phase. Detection wavelength chosen was 258 nm. **Result:** The retention factor (Rf) for Rilpivirine was found to be 0.52 ± 0.02 and retention factor (Rf) for Dolutegravir Sodium was found to be 0.24 ± 0.02 . The drugs were subjected to stress testing as per ICH Q1A (R2). There was no interference of any degradant at Rf of Rilpivirine and Dolutegravir Sodium. The developed method was successfully validated according to ICH Q2R1 guidelines. The calibration curve was found to be linear over a range of 400 - 2000 ng/ band. The accuracy of the method is indicated by good recovery in the range of 95.49% - 101.66% for Rilpivirine and of Dolutegravir Sodium 99.16% - 101.48% with less than 2% of RSD. The limit of detection and limit of quantification of Rilpivirine was found to be LOD-123.75 ng/band and LOQ-375.01 ng/band and for Dolutegravir Sodium was found to be LOD-109.03ng/band and 330.41ng/band. **Conclusion:** A new simple, accurate, precise and specific stability- indicating high performance thin layer chromatographic (HPTLC) method has been developed and validated for determination of Rilpivirine and Dolutegravir Sodium in combination. We have developed HPTLC method wherein the stress conditions were optimized to achieve 10-30 % degradation.

Corresponding author

Dr. Mrinalini C. Damle

Prof. Department of Quality Assurance,
All India Shri Shivaji Memorial Society's College of Pharmacy,
Kennedy Road, near R.T.O.,
Pune-411001, Maharashtra, India
mcdamle@rediffmail.com
+919860230912

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INTRODUCTION

Rilpivirine^[1] is chemically 4-{{4-{{4-{{(1E)-2-cyanoeth-1-en-1-yl}}-2,6-dimethylphenyl}} amino) pyrimidin-2-yl} amino} benzonitrile. Rilpivirine^[1] is the second generation of non-nucleoside reverse transcriptase inhibitors (NNRTIS) recently marketed for the treatment of HIV infection. It is superior to the first generation NNRTI in that it is active against NNRTI resistant HIV-I. It is a diarylpyrimidine, a class of molecules that resemble pyrimidine nucleotides found in DNA. Because of its flexible chemical structure, resistance of Rilpivirine is less likely to develop than other NNRTI's. Dolutegravir^[2-3], (4R,12aS)-N-(2,4-difluorobenzyl)-7-hydroxy-4-methyl-6,8-dioxo-3,4,6,8,12,12a-hexahydro-2H-pyrido[1',2':4,5]pyrazino[2,1-b][1,3]oxazine-9-carboxamide. Dolutegravir is integrase inhibitor used in the treatment of HIV and was approved by FDA. Dolutegravir works by blocking integrase, an HIV enzyme. This prevents HIV from replicating and lowers the amount of HIV in the blood. It can be used in the treatment of HIV in both adults and children of 12 years age and older and weighing at least 40 kilograms. Literature review revealed that UV^[4], HPTLC^[5,6] and^[7-13] HPLC methods have been reported for analysis of Rilpivirine and Dolutegravir sodium as a single form and in combination with other drugs. There is no reported method is available for simultaneous estimation of Rilpivirine and Dolutegravir sodium by HPTLC in combination. The work describes new adoptable method for simultaneous quantitation of Rilpivirine and Dolutegravir Sodium by HPTLC in combination. Janssen^[14] announces Two-drug Combination of Dolutegravir and Rilpivirine Demonstrates Efficacy in Maintaining Viral Suppression in Phase III. Study results presented by Janssen indicate that combination of Rilpivirine and Dolutegravir Sodium can be very promising in future for two Drug regimens; for HIV patients. Hence stability indicating method has been developed for this combination. As per ICH Q1 R2^[15-16] guidelines the method was validated.

Fig: 1 Structure of Dolutegravir Sodium.

Fig: 2 Structure of Rilpivirine.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Reagents and chemicals:

Working standard of Rilpivirine and Dolutegravir Sodium were obtained from Mylan Labs, Hyderabad and Lupin Laboratories Ltd, Aurangabad. Methanol (AR grade), Toluene (AR grade), Ethyl Acetate (AR grade), Tri Ethyl Amine (TEA), Hydrochloric acid (HCl), Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂, 30% & 6% v/v), Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) were purchased from LOBA CHEMIE Pvt. Ltd Mumbai.

Method development:

Method development for resolution of Rilpivirine and Dolutegravir Sodium was started with the development of densitogram with solvents in different ratios and combinations of methanol, chloroform and Toluene. Finally, Toluene: Methanol: Ethyl Acetate: Tri Ethyl Amine in the ratio of 5.5:1:1.5:0.1 v/v/v/v was selected as a mobile phase with a good resolution at R_f 0.52 ± 0.02 and 0.24 ± 0.02 for Rilpivirine and Dolutegravir Sodium respectively.

Preparation of standard stock solution:

Standard stock solutions of Rilpivirine and Dolutegravir Sodium were prepared by separately dissolving 10 mg of drug in 10 ml of methanol to get concentrations of 1000 µg/ml. From respective stock solution of Rilpivirine, 1 ml Stock in 10 ml of methanol to get concentration of 100 µg/ml and for Dolutegravir Sodium 1 ml of standard stock solution was diluted with methanol in 10 ml volumetric flask to get standard stock solution 100 µg/ml.

SELECTION OF DETECTION WAVELENGTH:

From the standard stock solution (1000 µg/ml) further dilutions were done using methanol and scanned over the range of 200 - 400 nm and the spectra was obtained. It was observed that showed considerable absorbance at 272nm (Rilpivirine) & 258 nm (Dolutegravir Sodium).

Fig 3: Absorbance spectra of 272nm (Rilpivirine) & 258 nm (Dolutegravir Sodium).

CHROMATOGRAPHIC STATE AND INSTRUMENTATION:

Chromatographic separation of drug was performed on Aluminum plates precoated with silica gel 60 F254 , (10cm × 10 cm with 250 μm layer thickness). Samples were applied on the plate as a band with 5 mm width using Camag 100 μl sample syringe (Hamilton, Switzerland) with a Linomat 5 applicator (Camag, Switzerland). The mobile phase was composed of Toluene: Methanol: Ethyl Acetate: Tri Ethyl Amine in the ratio of (5.5:1:1.5:0.1 v/v/v/v). 10 cm × 10 cm CAMAG twin trough glass chamber was used for linear ascending development of TLC plate under 20 mins saturation conditions and 10 ml of mobile phase solvent was used per run, migration distance was 90 mm. Densitometric scanning was performed using Camag TLC scanner 3 in the range of 400-200 nm, operated by winCATS software (Version 1.4.3, Camag), slit dimensions were 5.00 x 0.45 mm and Deuterium lamp was used as a radiation source.

STRESS DEGRADATION STUDIES OF DRUG:

Stress testing studies were carried out to provide evidence on how the quality of drug varies under the influence of variety of environmental conditions like hydrolysis under different pH conditions, oxidation, heat etc as per ICH Q1AR2 guidelines.

Alkali catalyzed hydrolysis

Base hydrolysis was done using 1 ml of solution of Rilpivirine mixed with 1 ml of 0.5N NaOH. The solution was diluted to 10 ml with methanol and spotted after 1 hr. 4μl of the solution was spotted. 10 times higher concentration were also spotted to locate degradation product, if any. Same procedure was repeated for working standard solution of Dolutegravir Sodium with 0.1N NaOH, and spotted after 1 hr. First the degradation was tried with 0.1 N NaOH for 1 hr, degradation observed was too low. So later harsh condition was used 0.5N NaOH for Rilpivirine was used.

Acid Catalyzed Hydrolysis

The solution was exposed to Acid hydrolysis 1 ml of solution of Rilpivirine was mixed with 1 ml of 0.5N HCl. The solution was diluted to 10 ml with methanol and spotted after 1 hr. 4μl of the solution was spotted. 10 times higher concentration were also spotted to locate degradation product, if any. Same procedure was repeated for working standard solution of Dolutegravir Sodium with 0.1N HCl, and spotted after 1 hr. First the degradation was tried with 0.1 N HCl for 1 hour degradation observed was too low. So later harsh condition was used 0.5N HCl for Rilpivirine was used.

Oxidation Degradation

For Oxidative studies, 30% v/v of H₂O₂ for Rilpivirine and 6% v/v of H₂O₂ for Dolutegravir Sodium was used. 1 ml of solution of Rilpivirine was mixed with 1 ml of 30% H₂O₂. The solution was diluted to 10 ml with methanol and spotted after 1 hr. 4μl of the solution was spotted. 10 times higher concentration were also spotted to locate degradation product, if any. Same procedure was repeated for working standard solution of Dolutegravir Sodium with 6% H₂O₂, and spotted after 1 hr. First the degradation was tried with 6% H₂O₂ for 1 hour degradation observed was too low. So later harsh conditions were used 30% H₂O₂ for Rilpivirine was used.

Degradation under Dry Heat

Dry heat studies were performed by keeping drug sample of Rilpivirine in oven (60°C) for a period of 2 hrs. Sample were withdrawn and dissolved in methanol and diluted to get 1000μg/ml as stock solution. Stock solution was diluted to 100 μg/ml concentration of 4 μl was spotted. 10 times higher concentration were also spotted to locate degradation product, if any. Dolutegravir Sodium was exposed to 60°C for 2 hrs and solution was prepared as sample were withdrawn and dissolved in methanol and diluted to get 1000μg/ml as stock solution. From Stock 1 ml was pipette out i.e. 100 μg/ml concentration of 4 μl was used.

Photo-Degradation

Photolytic studies were also carried out by exposure of drug to UV light up to 200 watt hours/square meter and subsequently to cool fluorescent light to achieve an illumination of 1.2 million Lux hr. Samples were withdrawn and dissolved in methanol and diluted to get 1000 μ g/ml as stock solution. 100 μ g/ml concentration of 4 μ l was spotted. 10 times higher concentration were also spotted to locate degradation product, if any. Dolutegravir Sodium was exposed to UV and Fluorescence solution was prepared as sample were withdrawn and dissolved in methanol and diluted to get 1000 μ g/ml as stock solution. From Stock 1 ml was pipette out i.e. 100 μ g/ml concentration of 4 μ l was spotted.

PREPARATION OF TABLET SOLUTION FOR ASSAY:

Blend was prepared using Starch and Lactose as blank blend into which drugs were spiked. From this powder mixture, certain amount (equivalent to 50 mg of Rilpivirine and 50 mg of Dolutegravir) of the powder was accurately weighed and transferred to 10 ml volumetric flask. Methanol was added in the volumetric flask and the resultant mixture was sonicated for 10 min at room temperature to disperse the powder completely. The resultant mixture was further diluted to 10 ml with methanol and then filtered through Whatmann filter paper no 1, to get the clear solution. 1 ml aliquot of the filtered solution was then diluted to 10 ml with methanol in 10 ml volumetric flask to get the final concentration 1000 μ g/ml. 4 μ l of 1000 μ g/ml of this solution was spotted on TLC plate as a band of length 6 mm on two separate tracks for the assay of Rilpivirine and Dolutegravir Sodium.

METHOD VALIDATION

The method was validated as per ICH Q2R1 guidelines:

Specificity:

The specificity of the method was ascertained by peak purity profiling studies. Purity of the drug peak was ascertained by analyzing the spectrum at peak start, middle and at peak end. The peak purity was determined on TLC scanner 3 using WinCATS software (version 1.4.3).

Linearity and Range:

Linearity was studied by analyzing five concentrations of the drug, and process was repeated for five times each. It was done over the concentration range of 400-2000 ng/band and 400-2000 ng/band for Rilpivirine and Dolutegravir Sodium respectively.

Accuracy:

To check accuracy of the method, recovery studies were carried out by addition of standard drug solution to pre-analyzed sample solution at three different levels of 80, 100 and 120 %. Mean percentage recovery for both the drugs was then determined

Precision:

Precision of the system and method was evaluated by analyzing independent sample preparations obtained from homogenous sample and % RSD value obtained was calculated to determine any variation.

Limit of detection and limit of Quantitation:

The detection limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analytes in a sample, which can be detected but not necessarily quantities as an exact value.

Robustness

The robustness of an analytical procedure is a measure of its capacity to remain unaffected by small, but deliberate variations in method parameters and provides an indication of its reliability during normal usage. Robustness of the method was determined by making slight deliberate changes like chamber saturation time and \pm 2% variation in mobile phase compositions.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Optimization of mobile phase:

The analytical method was developed by studying different parameters. First of all, maximum absorbance was found to be at 258 nm. The stationary phase used for study of Rilpivirine and Dolutegravir Sodium was Aluminium plates pre-coated with silica gel 60 F254, (10 cm \times 10 cm with 250 μ m layer thickness. Different ratios of mobile phase constituents were studied, mobile phase with Toluene: Methanol: Ethyl acetate: Tri Ethyl Amine in the ratio of (5.5:1:1.5:0.1 v/v/v/v) was chosen due to good symmetrical peak. The Retention factor (Rf) for Rilpivirine was found to be 0.52 and retention factor (Rf) for Dolutegravir Sodium was found to be 0.20. The analytical method was found linear over the range of 400-2000ng/band.

FORCED DEGRADATION STUDIES:

Forced degradation studies were conducted to evaluate the stability and specificity of the method. No degradation products was observed when the drug was subjected to acidic, basic and neutral treatment, exposure to UV light, heat and to oxidation conditions. The drug peaks obtained from all the stressed samples were found to be homogenous and pure. The drug was found to be photo labile. Hence the method is found to be specific. The results are given in Table: 1 & 2

Table 1: Summary of stress degradation of Rilpivirine Stress degradation conditions

Sr.No	Stress degradation conditions of Rilpivirine	Percent degraded (%)
1.	Base (0.5 N NaOH, kept for 1 hr)	16.52
2.	Acid (0.5 N HCl, Kept for 1 hr)	19.62
3.	H ₂ O ₂ 30% v/v (kept for 1 hr)	19.13
4.	Dry Heat (60°C, 2hrs)	13.05
5.	Photo stability (UV, 200 watt hrs/square meter)	19.11
6.	Florescence (1.2 million Lux. Hrs)	11.86

Table 2: Summary of stress degradation of Dolutegravir Sodium Stress degradation conditions.

Sr.No	Stress degradation conditions of Dolutegravir Sodium	Percent degraded (%)
1.	Base (0.1 N NaOH, kept for 1 hr)	20.09
2.	Acid (0.1 N HCl, Kept for 1 hr)	18.11
3.	H ₂ O ₂ 6% v/v (kept for 1 hr)	17.51
4.	Dry Heat (60°C, 2hrs)	18.48
5.	Photo stability (UV, 200 watt hrs/square meter)	19.37
6.	Florescence (1.2 million Lux. Hrs)	15.12

METHOD VALIDATION**Specificity:**

The specificity of the method was ascertained by peak purity profiling studies in winCATS software. It involves comparison of UV spectra at peak start, middle and end. The peak purity values were found to be more than 0.998, indicating the non interference of any other peak of degradation product or impurity.

Table 3: Specificity.

Peak purity at 258nm				
Parameters	Rilpivirine		Dolutegravir Sodium	
	r(s,m)	r(m,e)	r(s,m)	r(m,e)
Initial	0.9993	0.9998	0.9992	0.9998
Base(0.5N & 0.1N 1 hr)	0.9946	0.9868	0.9979	0.9953
Acid(0.5N & 0.1N 1 hr)	0.9914	0.9998	0.9964	0.9992
H ₂ O ₂ (30% v/v & 6% v/v)	0.9993	0.9956	0.9962	0.9986
Heat(60°C 2 hrs)	0.9997	0.9875	0.9991	0.9998
UV(200 watt hrs/square meter)	0.9994	0.9997	0.9995	0.9990
Fluorescence(1.2 million Lux.hrs)	0.9995	0.9994	0.9991	0.9994

Linearity and Range:

The linear calibration range was found to be 400 to 2000ng/band. The calibration curve obtained by the least square regression analysis between average peak area and concentration showed linear relationship with a correlation coefficient of $r^2 = 0.990$ (Rilpivirine) AND $r^2 = 0.980$ (Dolutegravir Sodium) .The equation of the calibration curve found for Rilpivirine was $y = 3.896x + 2349$ and for Dolutegravir Sodium was

$$y=5.596x+5704.$$

Fig: 4 Linearity of Dolutegravir Sodium (400-2000ng/band) and Rilpivirine (400-2000ng/band).

Assay:

Assay was performed on blend of bulk drugs plus excipients. It was determined by extrapolation of peak area was found to be 98.09% and 102.80% for Dolutegravir Sod and Rilpivirine.

Accuracy:

The accuracy of the developed method was established by standard addition method by adding known standard concentration solutions to the pre-analyzed samples in different levels, i.e., 80, 100 and 120 %. The samples were analyzed for five times at each level. The mean recovery and RSD values were calculated. This is in accordance with ICH guidelines. Therefore method was found to be accurate. Recovery of Rilpivirine was found to be 96.27% - 99.26% with less than 1.226% of RSD value and of Dolutegravir Sodium was found to be 98.54% - 101.07% with less than 1.2334%, indicating that the proposed method.

Table 4: Recovery Studies of Rilpivirine and Dolutegravir Sodium.

Drug	Amount spotted (ng band ⁻¹)	Total amount found (ng band ⁻¹)	% Recovery	% RSD
1. Rilpivirine	800	763.9	95.49	0.925
	1200	1038.7	102.82	1.176
	1600	1255.9	101.66	0.122
2. Dolutegravir Sodium	800	793.82	99.16	0.836
	1200	1006.2	100.60	0.173
	1600	1217.8	101.48	1.212

Precision

The RSD values for intraday and interday-precision were not more than 2 %, indicating the repeatability and reproducibility of the method.

Table 5: Precision (INTRA DAY).

Conc. (ng/ml)	Area		Mean Area		Mean SD		%RSD	
	RILP	DOLU	RILP	DOLU	RILP	DOLU	RILP	DOLU
800	9540.3	6230.2						
	9632.2	6379.6	9701.5	6244.20	4.215	2.064	1.966	2.095
	9932.1	6122.7						
1200	12224.1	9410.3						
	12123.2	9243.2	12122	9259.23	1.392	1.533	1.550	1.616
	12021.1	9124.2						
1600	14162.6	14203.2						
	15145.2	14011.2	14777	14072.8	1.4980	0.903	1.984	0.823
	15025.6	14004.2						

Table 6: Precision (INTER DAY).

Conc. (ng/ml)	Area		Mean Area		SD		%RSD	
	RILPI	DOLU	RILPI	DOLU	RILPI	DOLU	RILPI	DOLU
800	9840.3	6330.21						
	9932.2	6379.65	9901.53	6377.54	1.150	0.741	1.225	1.985
	9902.1	6422.76						
1200	12224	10221.1						
	12123	10123.1	12122.6	10121.8	1.467	1.066	1.550	1.616
	12021	10021.2						
1600	13122.6	13203.2						
	12125.2	13011.2	12757.8	13139.5	0.615	0.889	0.755	0.870
	13025.6	13204.2						

Limit of detection and quantification (LOD and LOQ):

The LOD (Limit of Detection) and LOQ (Limit of Quantitation) were estimated from the standard deviation of the lowest response and the slope of the calibration curve.

Table 7: LOD & LOQ.

Drugs	LOD(ng/band)	LOQ(ng/band)
Rilpivirine	123.75	375.01
Dolutegravir Sodium	109.03	330.41

Robustness

The %RSD values of all robustness parameters were examined and found to be within the limit of 2%, showed that the proposed method was robust.

Table: 8 Robustness.

Sr. No.	Parameter	Robust condition	% RSD	
			Rilpivirine	Dolutegravir Sodium
1.	Saturation time (20 mins) ± 5 min.	15 mins	1.345	0.818
		25 mins	0.293	0.590
2.	Mobile phase composition v/v/v/v	5.5:1:1.4:0.1	1.754	0.620
		5.4:1:1.5:0.1	1.646	0.645
3.	Time from spotting to development (immediate)	0 min	1.801	0.496
		25 mins	1.651	1.870
4.	Detection Wavelength	258 nm	1.152	0.272
		260nm	1.185	1.115

Table 9: Summary of validation study.

Sr. No.	Validation parameters	Results					
		(Rilpivirine)		(Dolutegravir Sodium)			
1.	Specificity	Specific		Specific			
2.	Linearity Range	$y = 3.896x + 2349, r^2 = 0.990$		$y = 5.596x + 5704, r^2 = 0.980$			
3.	% Recovery	80%	95.49	80%	99.16		
		100%	102.82	100%	100.60		
		120%	101.66	120%	101.48		
4.	A) Interday precision	Precision					
		%RSD		%RSD			
		800	1.225	1200	1.985		
		1200	1.550	1600	1.616		
		1600	0.755	800	0.872		
		A) Intraday precision		800	1.966	1200	2.095
				1200	1.550	1600	1.616
				1600	1.984		0.823
5.	Limit of Detection (ng/band)	123.75		109.03			
6.	Limit of Quantitation (ng/band)	375.01		330.41			
7.	Robustness	Robust		Robust			

DISCUSSION

S.S.Chitlange *et al* [6] have reported Stability Indicating HPTLC method for the Simultaneous estimation of Rilpivirine, Emtricitabine and Tenofovir in Bulk and Combined Pharmaceutical Dosage Form. In this work, mild conditions were used like 0.1N for Acid and Base hydrolysis, 6% for oxidation but no degradation was observed for Rilpivirine.

T. Sreenivasulu Reddy *et al* [7] have reported a validated stability indicating HPLC assay method for Rilpivirine HCl in bulk drug. In this work, HPLC method was developed by using gradient elution and harsh stress conditions were used like 1N & 5N acid/base for hydrolysis, 30% H₂O₂ for Oxidation and very long duration of 7 days for Thermal stress at 60°C, but no degradation was observed.

We have developed HPTLC method wherein the stress conditions were optimized to achieve 10-30 % degradation.

CONCLUSION

The developed method is economic, simple, rapid, and high through-put. It can be used to monitor stability of Rilpivirine and Dolutegravir Sodium.

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